

Pre-main sequence stars in the time domain: insights from high-precision, space-borne photometry

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Abstract

High-precision time series photometry provides a unique window into the dynamics of the inner disk regions (< 1 AU) around young stars (< 5 -10 Myr). Exquisite surveys carried out with *CoRoT*, *Kepler*, and *TESS* have revealed a huge variety of photometric behaviors for young stellar objects, driven by variable mass accretion, stellar magnetic activity, or rapidly evolving circumstellar dust structures. This variety of behaviors, observed in each young cluster and star-forming region investigated from space, points to a coexistence of distinct paradigms of star-disk interaction that may govern different stages of pre-main sequence evolution. Thanks to the *K2* mission, accurate time domain data for hundreds of young stars are now available for virtually every stage of protoplanetary disk lifetimes, across different stellar mass regimes from cool stars and beyond: surveyed regions range from ρ Ophiuchus and the Lagoon Nebula (~ 2 Myr), to NGC 2264 (3-5 Myr, monitored earlier with *CoRoT*), to Upper Scorpius (5-10 Myr). In this contribution, we discuss the insights provided by those campaigns into the time evolution of inner disks around young stars, and what these observations teach us regarding the stellar and circumstellar dynamics as a function of stellar mass and environmental conditions.

1 Introduction

Over the past decades, instrumental advances in the areas of polarimetric differential imaging and interferometry have allowed the scientific community to achieve reconstructed images of the protoplanetary disks around young stars in unprecedented detail (e.g., Garufi *et al.*, 2018; Long *et al.*, 2018). However, these methods are often unable to resolve the innermost astronomical unit (AU) of circumstellar disks, where the magnetospheric interaction between the inner disk and the central star develops. A key regulator of this interaction is the mass transfer from the disk to the star, which occurs via accretion streams or columns channeled along the stellar magnetic field lines (for a review, see Hartmann *et al.*, 2016). The accelerated gas in the accretion streams is responsible for the distinctive emission line profiles (most prominently in H α) that are associated with accreting young stars, while excess continuum emission, most visible at ultraviolet (UV) wavelengths, arises from the accretion shocks formed where near free-falling material accretes onto the star. When combined with optical and infrared (IR) observations, which trace the stellar and disk contributions to the total flux emitted by the system, these diagnostics offer a privileged window onto the structure and dynamics of the inner disk regions.

Photometric variability is a long-appreciated characteristic of young stellar objects (YSOs; e.g., Joy, 1945), and manifests ubiquitously across the wavelength spectrum and on every timescale from hours to decades (see Fischer *et al.*, 2022 for a recent review). Statistical surveys of young stellar variability indicate that intermediate timescales of days to weeks (which encompass the measured rotation rate distributions for these objects) tend to dominate the variability behaviors observed up to timescales of several years (e.g., Costigan *et al.*, 2014; Venuti *et al.*, 2014, 2015; Flaischlen *et al.*, 2022). Three main factors contribute to shaping the flux vari-

ation trends observed for young stars over these intermediate timescales: *i*) stellar magnetic activity and rotational modulation effects induced by starspots; *ii*) rapid accretion shock evolution induced by erratic accretion streams and time-variable mass transfer efficiency; *iii*) viewing geometry to the specific star-disk system and varying visibility of inner disk structures along the stellar rotation cycle. By assembling a multi-wavelength picture of stellar variability in young open clusters of different ages, we are able to map the dynamical evolution of inner disk processes across the protoplanetary disk lifetimes.

2 A space-borne view of YSO variability

Preliminary atlases of YSO variability behaviors and their physical drivers were established thanks to pioneering surveys in the 1980s (Herbst *et al.*, 1994, and references therein). While these studies enabled recognizing the photometric signatures of each of the three main sources of YSO variability enumerated in Sect. 1, the inherent limitations of ground-based observations (day/night alternation; changing weather conditions) prevented a detailed description of small-scale light curve patterns that could match theoretical predictions under different assumptions. The paradigm started shifting in the 2000s with the advent of space-based observatories, notably *Spitzer* in the mid-IR, then *CoRoT* and *Kepler* in the optical. Thanks to photometric precisions $\sim 10^{-3}$ mag and nearly uninterrupted observing campaigns over weeks to months for each targeted cluster, these observatories brought about a first uniform depiction of the manifold variability behaviors typical of active YSOs, and enabled parsing the diverse timescales embedded in the stellar light curves and associated with different variability signatures.

The extent and homogeneity of space-borne photometric time series for young stars led to the implementation of first

quantitative metrics for their classification (Cody *et al.*, 2014), based upon two main light curve characteristics: the degree of periodicity or repetitiveness of flux variations, and the balance between brightening events and fading events around the typical brightness state of the source. The resulting light curve classification encompasses and expands earlier sorting schemes built on visual inspection, and revealed at least eight¹ separate morphology types among disk-bearing YSOs:

- *periodic* (no cycle-to-cycle changes in light curve shape and/or amplitude);
- *quasi-periodic symmetric* (clear periodicity but changes in shape and/or amplitude from one cycle to the next);
- *stochastic* (no obvious periodicity in variation pattern);
- *bursting* (no obvious light curve periodicity and prevalence of brightening events along the time series);
- *aperiodic dipping* (no obvious periodicity and prevalence of fading events along the time series);
- *quasi-periodic dipping* (prevalence of fading events that repeat at regular intervals along the time series, albeit with changes in shape and/or amplitude of the flux dip);
- *flat-line* (no discernible variability pattern);
- *long-timescale* variable.

An illustration of this quantitative classification scheme and of its interpretation can be found in Fig. 1. For periodic and quasi-periodic variables, the observed variability patterns are well represented by rotational modulation induced by a combination of dark starspots and longer-lived accretion shocks at the stellar surface. In these cases, the recurrence timescales mirror the stellar rotation rate, while the variability amplitudes and their wavelength dependence provide an indication of the spot properties (effective temperature relative to the star; area coverage) and distribution. In turn, the latter can be used as a proxy to infer some global information on the surface structure of the stellar magnetic field (see Sect. 3).

Erratic variables, instead, exhibit light curve patterns that match theoretical expectations for YSOs accreting in an unstable regime (Kulkarni & Romanova, 2008; Kurosawa & Romanova, 2013). In this scenario, plasma instabilities of Rayleigh-Taylor type develop at the interface between the high-density inner disk and the stellar magnetosphere. This instability prevents the disk matter from being channeled along the magnetospheric lines, and leads to the formation of discrete tongues of material that propagate horizontally across the field lines until they encounter a more intense magnetic field in the stellar proximity. Rather than forming extended accretion columns that start from the inner disk towards the stellar magnetic poles, these streams will therefore be channeled towards the star in small-scale accretion funnels only over a much shorter distance, falling onto the star close to the equatorial regions. This mechanism produces short-lived accretion shocks at random location across the

stellar surface, yielding irregular light curve profiles. Unstable star-disk interaction regimes are expected to be accompanied by high accretion rates \dot{M}_{acc} onto the star, and indeed the most erratic variables identified in young star clusters (bursting YSOs, characterized by intense brightening epochs that presumably trace the evolution of a single accretion event) were found to exhibit \dot{M}_{acc} values five times larger than those detected on other types of accreting YSOs (Venuti *et al.*, 2014). At more moderate \dot{M}_{acc} levels, erratic flux variations can also trace a time-variable efficiency of mass transfer across the inner disk, which results in stochastic modulation effects by the surface accretion shocks.

While the interpretation of modulated and erratic behaviors assumes a viewing geometry favorable to stellar surface features, dipping behaviors are best interpreted in terms of inner disk structures that repeatedly cross the line of sight to the system, thus concealing part of the stellar photosphere, for YSOs seen at near edge-on inclinations (e.g., Bodman *et al.*, 2017). In these cases, a well-defined periodicity in the dipping events may be detected if the star-disk system is interacting in a stable regime, while aperiodic dipping behaviors may trace unstable star-disk interaction patterns or short-term changes in the configuration of the magnetospheric field lines. For some star-forming regions monitored from space, complementary observations (notably with ALMA) have been employed to test the connection between inner and outer disk geometries around dipping variables. These surveys have confirmed a preference for dipper stars to host disks seen at high inclinations ($i \geq 50^\circ$; Cody & Hillenbrand, 2018); however, several notable cases of dipping behaviors on YSOs seen almost face-on have also been reported (Ansdell *et al.*, 2020), which may be explained by misalignments between disconnected inner and outer disks that can develop during the dynamical evolution of protoplanetary disks.

3 Mass- and age-dependent YSO variability

Following the dedicated monitoring campaign of YSO variability in the NGC 2264 cluster (age $\sim 3 - 5$ Myr) with *CoRoT*, several additional star-forming regions were mapped during the *Kepler/K2* mission: Taurus, ρ Ophiuchus, and the Lagoon Nebula (all aged $\leq 1 - 3$ Myr), and Upper Scorpius (age $\sim 5 - 10$ Myr). Taken together, these regions encompass the entire range of protoplanetary disk lifetimes, and therefore provide a sequential view of how the dynamics of YSO variability evolves as a function of age.

3.1 Lagoon Nebula: YSO variability vs. mass

Among the clusters listed above, the Lagoon Nebula stands out thanks to its comparatively higher-mass YSO population, which renders it an ideal target to explore any mass-dependent trends in young stellar behaviors. A statistical analysis of the light curves exhibited by its members (Venuti *et al.*, 2021) confirmed the presence of all distinct variability patterns categorized in the other regions, in particular:

- regular modulated behaviors (comprising $\sim 50\%$ of Lagoon Nebula YSOs, with amplitudes $\sim 19\%$ - 26% in flux);
- erratic behaviors ($\sim 25\%$ of Lagoon Nebula YSOs, with amplitudes between $\sim 55\%$ in flux for stochastic variables and $\sim 125\%$ in flux for bursting variables);

¹For a ninth variable class, the *eclipsing binary* systems, the most prominent flux variations are not caused by the dynamics of the primary star but by the transiting stellar companion.

Figure 1: Imprints of distinct modes and geometries of star-disk interaction on the observed YSO variability behaviors. The central panel, taken from Cody *et al.* (2014), illustrates the statistical metrics developed to classify YSO light curves upon two parameters: Q (which measures the degree of periodicity/stochasticity of the observed flux variations, and M (which measures the prevalence of brightening vs. fading events in the light curve. Datapoints plotted on this panel show the metric results when applied to YSOs in the NGC 2264 cluster, monitored with the *CoRoT* satellite. The morphology of representative light curves that would fall onto different areas of the diagram is exemplified by the six *CoRoT* light curves of NGC 2264 members distributed around the panel (Cody *et al.*, 2014; Venuti *et al.*, 2017). The two panels located at the same height, near $M = 0.0$, on opposite sides with respect to the central diagram illustrate two distinct regimes of star-disk interaction: the first (on the left) leading to stable accretion flows channeled along a dipolar magnetosphere that can be inclined with respect to the stellar rotation axis (from Romanova *et al.*, 2004); the second (on the right) leading to unsteady, equatorial accretion tongues driven by instabilities between the inner disk and the stellar magnetosphere (from Kulkarni & Romanova, 2008). Stable patterns lead to longer-lived accretion features and a noticeable periodicity in the light curves, whereas unsteady patterns lead to rapidly evolving accretion features and to erratic flux variations. The bottom panel to the left of the central diagram (located near $M = 1.0 - 1.5$) sketches the geometry of an accreting star-disk system seen almost edge-on, with recurring occultations of the stellar photosphere by a non-axisymmetric accretion curtain as the system rotates (from Bouvier *et al.*, 1999). Similar viewing geometries are believed to be responsible for the photometric behaviors of young stars classified as dippers.

- dipping behaviors ($\sim 15\%$ of Lagoon Nebula YSOs, with variability amplitudes $\sim 78\%-93\%$ in flux).

However, noticeable mass-dependent effects in the statistical distribution of variability properties were detected across the cluster: flat-line light curves were found to be more common among earlier-type stars (A/F spectral types) than later-type stars (G/K spectral types), and dipping behaviors were not observed among stars with spectral types earlier than G. The latter finding can be understood by considering simple constraints for the formation and survival of dust structures in the inner disk that can conceal the star as the system rotates. Typical period measurements derived from dipper light curves, both for the fading events and for the out-of-dip variability, strongly indicate that the dust structures responsible for the dipping pattern are located near the corotation radius, where the disk Keplerian velocity equals the stellar rotation rate. For dust structures to survive at this position, the corotation radius needs to be located beyond the sublimation radius, which is the minimum distance from the star at which matter can exist in non-sublimated form. As the temperature of the star increases, the sublimation radius is pushed outward, at longer rotation periods, and a comparison with pre-main sequence evolutionary models indicates that, by the G-to-F transition, the minimum orbital period of disk dust structures is much longer than the typical rotation rates measured for young stars (see Fig. 14 of Venuti *et al.*, 2021). This implies that, for young stars with spectral types earlier than G, dust cannot exist at the corotation radius.

The *K2* light curves of Lagoon Nebula members were also analyzed in detail to study how the intensity of flux variations changes as a function of variability timescale across the time series, using the structure function approach (Sergison *et al.*, 2020). This study, too, revealed some significant mass-dependent trends: in particular, lower-mass stars (spectral classes G and K) were found to exhibit significantly larger normalized variability amplitudes than higher-mass stars (spectral classes B and A). This trend was observed across all timescales of interest that could be extracted from the *K2* light curves (i.e., ranging from 0.04-35.5 days), and across all light curve variability classes discussed in Sect. 2 (in the sense that, within each individual light curve class, earlier-type objects appear less variable than later-type objects; see Fig. 12 of Venuti *et al.*, 2021). Part of this trend could be explained by the fact that disk-related phenomena can be detected more frequently around lower-mass stars. However, the ubiquitous nature of this trend across the Lagoon Nebula population, including among members of variability classes not directly associated with disk-driven activity (for instance, flat-line or periodic variables), supports a different origin, related to the surface structure of the stellar magnetic field.

As discussed in Sect. 2, modulated variability amplitudes over rotational timescales reflect the flux contrast between the stellar photosphere and the spotted surface that can be observed at different phases. Well-organized surface magnetic fields, dominated by a dipolar component, are expected to produce large, localized spots at the magnetic poles, with a corresponding visibility that would be highly dependent on the stellar rotation phase. On the other hand, more chaotic magnetic field configurations, dominated by higher-order components, would lead to a more uniform distribution of dark spots at the stellar surface; as a consequence, the apparent contrast between stellar surface and spotted area would

not change significantly from one rotational phase to the next, and the resulting modulation effect over the full rotation period would be considerably smaller. When compared with the mass-dependent variability trends discussed above, this picture suggests that the magnetic field properties at the surface of young stars may change as a function of stellar mass/spectral type: a more ordered configuration, leading to large variability amplitudes, for lower-mass stars, and a more chaotic configuration, leading to small variability amplitudes, for higher-mass stars.

3.2 The *K2* view of inner disk evolution

While not providing additional constraints on the mass dependence of YSO variability, due to the more limited stellar mass spectrum covered by their populations, the other clusters targeted with *K2* help building a tentative evolutionary sequence for low-mass YSOs and their dynamics of star-disk interaction.

Indeed, a comparative analysis of light curve classification results among members of Taurus, ρ Ophiuchus, and Upper Scorpius (Cody *et al.*, 2022) provides some preliminary indications on evolutionary patterns for YSO variability:

- the percentage of dipper stars tends to increase with cluster age;
- the percentage of erratic variables tends to decrease with cluster age;
- the percentage of quasi-periodic bursting behaviors tends to decrease with cluster age;
- the overall variability amplitudes tend to decrease with cluster age.

Taken together, these trends paint a picture where young stars evolve towards weaker disk signatures as their age increases, consistent with observations of decreasing accretion activity and decreasing \dot{M}_{acc} values as disks transition from primordial to more evolved.

4 Summary

Monitoring the time behavior of young stars provides a direct window onto the structure of the inner disk environment, at a crucial stage for stellar evolution and planet formation. Dedicated space-based observational campaigns, conducted especially with *CoRoT* and *Kepler*, have revealed that young stars exhibit a variety of photometric behaviors (modulated, erratic, dipping). These are driven by a combination of several factors, such as surface magnetic activity, mass accretion onto the star, and inner disk geometry.

For any light curve morphology, low-mass stars are found to be more variable than high-mass stars, which can be understood in terms of a mass-dependent magnetic field structure in YSOs. Additional mass-dependent trends include the disappearance of dipping behaviors for spectral types earlier than G, possibly caused by the higher surface temperatures and more chaotic magnetic fields of higher-mass stars that prevent the formation and survival of inner disk dust structures in corotation with the star.

The comprehensive picture of YSO variability built over the last decade indicates that the observed variability amplitudes among low-mass stars tend to decrease with cluster age across the protoplanetary disk lifetimes. This trend

is accompanied by a decrease in the frequency of recurring erratic behaviors and an increase in more ordered behaviors, like quasi-periodic dippers, which are symptomatic of weaker disks and less intense accretion activity.

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